

Empowering the future: impact and opportunities of micro and small enterprises in the sustainable development of the amazon region - an empirical approach

Benjamín Roldan Polo Escobar

PhD. in Public Management and Governance. D. in Education Administration. Master in Strategic Management in Information Technologies. Mg. in Health Services Management. Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Toribio Rodríguez de Mendoza de Amazonas.

Carlos Alberto Hinojosa Salazar

PhD. in Administration. Master in Economic Sciences, mention in Finance. Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Toribio Rodríguez de Mendoza de Amazonas.

Julio Arevalo Reategui

PhD in Public Management and Governance, Master in Public Management, Economist, with experience in the public sector for more than 23 years. Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Toribio Rodríguez de Mendoza de Amazonas - Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences - Professional School of Economics - Undergraduate. Post-graduate professor at the National University of Ucayali (Pucallpa) and post-graduate professor at the National University of San Martín (Tarapoto).

Heisely Mori Pelaez

PhD in Science for Sustainable Development. Master in Management for Sustainable Development. Master in Public Management. Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Toribio Rodríguez de Mendoza de Amazonas.

Milena Leticia Weepiu Samekash

PhD. in Education. Master in Public Management. Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Toribio Rodríguez de Mendoza.

Juan Manuel Buendía Fernández

PhD. in Administration; Master of Science with mention in Investment Projects. Affiliation: Universidad Nacional Toribio Rodríguez de Mendoza.

ABSTRACT: In a scenario where the future demands sustainable development, Micro and Small Enterprises (MYPES) emerge as key players in the Amazon Region being important for their contribution to sustainable development and their ability to generate employment, promote economic inclusion and strengthen local economies, this study analyzes the transformative power of MYPES, the overall objective that seeks to obtain a comprehensive view of the impact and opportunities that Micro and Small Enterprises (MYPES) that generate sustainable development of the Amazonas Region - Peru. It explores the opportunities they provide to the business network, their access to global markets and collaborative alliances. The research used the non-experimental design - Transectional - Descriptive, correlational. The methodology of this study was based on a mixed approach. The population was 2254 companies, where the sample was 113 establishments. In the study, exemplary cases of countries were identified that reflect similar approaches that allow knowing the level of skills within the labor market. A questionnaire was applied to focus on the main characteristics of the different companies in the region, which was validated by three experts and proceeded to be validated with eleven SMEs, giving fairly reliable values identified with Cronbach's alpha of 0.815 and 0.823, respectively. The results emphasize the importance of strategies that connect communities, academic institutions and public policies through practical research, generating dialogue and joint solutions, with highly relevant impacts on regional development. In conclusion, MSEs are fundamental for sustainable development in the region, as they generate opportunities to promote social inclusion, improve the quality of life and promote environmentally responsible practices. Sustainable development indicators are important for decision-making and policy design to empower these enterprises and promote a sustainable future for the region.

Keywords: Sustainable development, sustainable future, micro and small enterprises (MSEs), Amazon region.

[Introduction](#)
[Methodology](#)
[Results](#)
[Discussion](#)
[Conclusions](#)
[References](#)

1. Introduction

Peru is currently undergoing a process of economic expansion and diversification, and for the Amazon this involves the extraction of non-renewable resources. Oil, mining and gas play an important role in the region's economy, along with agriculture and livestock. However, poverty and extreme poverty are still prevalent in the region, especially in the rural areas of the Amazon, where 54% of the population lives under these conditions (INEI, 2014). The Peruvian Amazon constitutes 60.6% of the country's territory, however, it is the least populated as it represents 9.41% of Peru's total population (UNICEF, 2014). This is an ethnically and linguistically diverse territory, as it is home to 60 of the 76 ethnic groups found in the country (INDEPA, 2010). Access roads to these areas of the Amazon are still restricted, and the provision of basic health, education, water and sanitation services remains a major challenge to be solved.

There are many projects to address the challenges of sustainable development in the Amazon Basin, but there is a gap in knowledge generation and management that makes it difficult to evaluate results and impacts. This limits the potential of successful projects and their ability to be replicated. Working solutions have been identified in the Amazon, but integrated solutions that recognize its environmental, social and cultural diversity are needed to achieve sustainable development in the region (UNDP 2016).

Currently, the role of Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) in the Peruvian Amazon region is extremely important, as they not only generate significant employment, but also play a crucial role in the socioeconomic progress of the local communities where they operate. Small businesses are considered to be the driving force behind economic growth, employment generation and poverty reduction in developing countries. In economic terms, when a micro or small business entrepreneur grows, he or she generates more employment because he or she demands more labor. In addition, its sales increase, and it achieves higher profits, which contributes, to a greater extent, to the formation of the gross domestic product (Okpara & Wynn, 2007).

Innovative Proposals for the Growth of Micro and Small Businesses:

Exploring New Approaches and Strategies Covin and Slevin's (1991) model highlights entrepreneurship which is positively associated with company financial performance and is related to technological sophistication, dynamism and hostile environment. He further suggests that entrepreneurial posture is more positively related to firm performance located among technologically advanced firms and in hostile environments, and among firms whose industries are in their early stages of the life cycle. In that sense, entrepreneurship is important for the financial success of the firm and is influenced by several factors, such as technological sophistication, dynamism and hostility of the environment.

The GEM project's strategic model measures the level of entrepreneurial activity and uncovers the factors that influence it. According to this model, the economic

development of countries is influenced by large multinational corporations and entrepreneurial activity, which requires a favorable environment and specific conditions to thrive. When both mechanisms act together, a synergistic effect is generated that drives economic growth (Serida et al., 2005). Ansoff's (1965) model classifies small business problems into three categories: managerial, operational and strategic. Operational decisions seek to maximize the profitability of ongoing operations, while strategic decisions focus on the appropriate selection of products and markets. Administrative decisions concern the structuring of the company's resources and the establishment of an environment conducive to the fulfillment of strategic functions. This model asks specific questions to address strategic problems and achieve the company's objectives.

Importance of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises in Peru

The importance of MSEs is evident from different angles. First, it is one of the main sources of employment; it is interesting as a tool for promoting employment insofar as it only requires an initial investment and allows access to low-income strata. Secondly, it can potentially become an important support for large companies by solving some production bottlenecks (Wong, 1997). This provides an opportunity for unemployed and low-income people to generate their own employment, and thus assist with the production of large companies.

Microenterprises have proven to be successful in transition economies such as Taiwan, where the majority are small and medium-sized enterprises. The flexible production of these companies is better adapted to segmented markets and specialized services, and the recent scientific-technological revolution will further enhance small productive units. New technologies make it easier to increase productivity at the personal or family level, communication favors lower-cost distribution, and high levels of schooling homogenize the labor force. Along these lines, microenterprises are a successful option in transition economies and are better adapted to segmented markets and specialized services (Orbe, 2008).

Problems in the development of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises in Peru

For at least the last 20 years, academia and experts in Peru, with arguments and evidence, have agreed on the need for major reforms to absorb the large informal labor sector, the most vulnerable. However, the majority of Congress and, until a few months ago, also the Executive with its Agenda 19, have continued to regulate in favor of the minority, the 24% formal sector, condemning the vast majority to continue being informal. Today, both are at fault for their inaction with respect to the progress made within the framework of this agenda (IPE, 2023). Current labor regulation cannot last forever without recognizing the economic reality and people's incentives and preferences. The advance of digital transformation, business innovation, the collaborative economy and the use of artificial intelligence exceed the state's capacity to regulate and oversee. Regulating these dynamics without understanding them may be a hard blow for the informal 76% and it is likely that Peruvian labor regulation will be applicable in the future to an increasingly smaller group (Gallardo, 2023).

Peruvian labor regulation will probably be applicable in the future to an increasingly smaller group of people, considering that the formal sector has a ceiling of around 30%. Three out of every four workers in the employed EAP are in informal employment, which represents a concern for improving the quality of life of citizens. In 2021, the informal sector was made up of 7 million 815 thousand productive units and represented 17.6% of the GDP. The Amazon region has an informal employment rate of 78.5% (INEI, 2022).

Social Responsibility (SR)

Galán & Sáenz de Miera (2012), Corporate social responsibility depends on the social demand to companies and is based on a society that demands decent labor relations, a democratic and human rights model and ecological commitment. So far, corporate SR has focused more on supply to markets than on social demand. However, everything points to the fact that society will be able to articulate and materialize this demand. Society can reward responsible companies in terms of consumption and financial investments, and punish them in the opposite case. Corporate social responsibility is based on a cause-effect relationship between sustainable practices and the market. In the 1980s, the UN created the World Commission on Environment and Development (Brundtland Commission). Its report stressed the need to achieve sustainable development, harmonizing economic growth, social cohesion and environmental conservation. The purpose is to safeguard ecosystems and future generations, guaranteeing global access to a decent quality of life (Garrido, 2005).

"Sustainable development" is a global term with varied interpretations. According to the Brundtland Commission, it involves balancing economy, society and environment to improve the quality of life. In addition, this entails the obligation to ensure the availability of resources in the future to achieve equitable welfare (Fernández, 2011). This allows us to base the general objective that seeks to obtain an integral vision of the impact and opportunities that Micro and Small Enterprises (MYPES) generate for the sustainable development of the Amazon Region -Peru. This objective seeks to understand how MSEs contribute to sustainable development in economic, social and environmental terms in that specific region.

2. Methodology

Study area

The focus of this study is on the Amazonas region of Peru, where we seek to analyze the social and environmental dimensions of MSEs, with a focus on sustainable development. The exploration and description are justified by previous limitations in research on sustainable development in SMEs. Through a mixed approach, the aim is to enrich the understanding of the topic, establishing interdisciplinary connections and exploring new perspectives in this context.

In order to achieve the objectives of this study, descriptive exploratory research is used. According to Namakforoosh, (2005), "The primary purpose of exploratory research is to obtain a broad perspective of the problem under consideration. These studies help us to break down a major challenge into more precise sub- problems, which in turn allows us to formulate hypotheses more clearly and concisely." This approach to inquiry is extremely valuable when knowledge of the subject matter is limited and the objective is to clarify the concepts associated with the research. In this way, it is possible to obtain a panoramic and close vision of a particular reality.

Its approach covers social, environmental and economic aspects, evaluating the actions of SMEs by means of statistical indexes to determine their contribution to sustainable development. In order to obtain relevant information on the common situations, customs and attitudes of SMEs, an instrument describing their activities and processes was used. The actions of the SMEs were evaluated in three key variables: social aspects, customs and attitudes, and were framed within a structure of corporate social responsibility and sustainable development.

Population, sample, sampling

The population within the framework of the departments: Amazonas, within the set of micro and small businesses there is a population of 2254 companies. Focused on retail

commerce, except automobiles. The sample consisted of 113 establishments, which were selected based on their productive activity and years of operation, considering a minimum of two years of activity. The research covered the period from June to December 2022. In order to evaluate the contribution of the SMEs' actions to sustainable development, a valuation index was created to measure their behavior and their level of relationship if these actions could be qualified as relevant activities that have an impact on sustainable development. Based on these considerations, 83 establishments were identified.

The sampling used was non-probability sampling characterized as purposive. According to Namakforoosh (2005), purposive sampling implies that the researcher carefully selects each sample element of the population based on his or her personal judgment. In this sampling approach, the researcher has prior knowledge of the elements to be investigated. Its use is justified by the availability and convenient location of the selected SMEs. This allows the researcher to have quick and easy access to the previously identified study subjects.

Data collection

The research instrument for the project "Perception of the sustainable development of SMEs in Peru" was developed. After submitting the original items to evaluation by judges, a final instrument of 27 questions was obtained, covering social, environmental and economic aspects. The present survey makes it possible to directly explore the actions of SMEs and to rate their performance in sustainable development. It combines quantitative and qualitative results to obtain a more complete and nuanced view of the relationship between socio-educational training and social commitment in companies. Implications and Actions: Interprets the findings in light of existing literature and highlights implications for education and society. Provides concrete recommendations for improving socioeducational training and fostering greater social engagement. Contribution and Relevance highlights how Spearman's correlation methodology and qualitative analysis offers a deeper and more robust perspective in understanding the relationship between variables. It highlights how this methodology enriches research in the educational and social field.

The survey was applied to 83 SMEs. Each item was measured using a Likert scale, with the following numbering: 1, Never; 2, Almost never; 3, Sometimes; 4, Almost always; and 5, Always. For validation, a pilot test was conducted in 11 SMEs located in the provinces of the Amazon region. The validation was carried out by three experts and the reliability by Cronbach's alpha was 0.815 and 0.823 respectively, which made it possible to determine that the instrument was appropriate for application to a sample of SMEs sampled in the Amazon region of northern Peru.

Socioformative education questionnaire

Dimensions	Indicators
Cognitive Dimension	You believe that your company's activities and programs promote learning and the development of new skills among employees.
	Strategies your company uses to foster creativity and innovation in its work teams.
	Opportunities for employees to share knowledge and experiences with each other to improve performance and productivity
Emotional Dimension	Does your company address the promotion of employees' emotional well-being and mental health in the workplace?
	Company initiatives to create an inclusive and respectful work environment that allows employees to express their emotions and opinions.
	Company measurement of employee emotional satisfaction as a key aspect of organizational success.
Social Dimension	Company's approach to collaboration and teamwork among employees
	Company contribution to the creation of a work environment that fosters diversity and inclusion.
	Company actions to establish positive ties with the local community and to promote social responsibility initiatives.
Ethical Dimension	Importance of ethical values and integrity in your company's decision making and behavior.
	Measures are taken in your company to ensure ethical and transparent business practices in all areas of your operation.
	The company promotes an organizational culture based on honesty, trust and social responsibility.

Social responsibility questionnaire

Dimensions	Indicators
Environmental Dimension	Practices your company adopts to minimize its environmental impact and promote sustainability
	Specific policies or strategies for the responsible management of natural resources in their environment.
	The company participates in local environmental conservation initiatives
Educational Dimension	In-house training to promote learning and skills development in employees
	Continuous training and knowledge acquisition among your staff
	Partnerships with educational institutions-region to strengthen education and training in your community
Community and Cultural Dimension	company initiatives to strengthen community ties and promote local cultural identity
	Contribution of the company to the welfare and development of the community in which it operates.
	Participation of the company in cultural projects, activities that preserve the culture of the region.
Technological Dimension	Degree of adoption of innovative technologies in your company's operations
	The company, technology to improve the efficiency, quality and competitiveness of its processes
	Technology investment plans to enhance innovation and development in your organization
Political Dimension	The company in the development of local policies and regulations affecting its sector.
	Promoting corporate social responsibility and civic engagement among employees
	Company participation in dialogue and collaboration initiatives with local authorities

The sampling used was non-probability sampling characterized as purposive. According to Namakforoosh (2005), purposive sampling implies that the researcher carefully selects each sample element of the population based on his or her personal judgment. In this sampling approach, the researcher has prior knowledge of the elements to be investigated. Its use is justified by the availability and convenient location of the selected SMEs. This allows the researcher to have quick and easy access to the previously identified study subjects.

The sample had selection criteria based on their productive activity and years of operation, considering a minimum of two years of activity. The research covered the period from June to December 2022. In order to evaluate the contribution of the SMEs' actions to

sustainable development, a valuation index was created to measure their behavior and their level of relationship if these actions could be qualified as relevant activities that have an impact on sustainable development.

3. Results

Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) have a significant social impact on improving the quality of life of the local population. Three key approaches highlight their positive influence: First, 56% benefited from employment accompanied by fair working conditions, MSEs contribute directly to improving people's economic situation, enabling them to meet their basic needs and prosper. Secondly, 65% are focused on the development of skills and capabilities of employees through training and professional growth, these companies open opportunities for a more promising working future and greater personal fulfillment. Third, 51% are immersed in promoting environmentally responsible production practices, MSEs protect the environment and ensure a healthy environment for future generations, which has a positive impact on the quality of life and general well-being of the community. These three approaches converge to highlight the fundamental role of MSEs in sustainable development and in creating an enabling environment for the prosperity and well-being of the local population.

Figure 1. Social Impact: Perspectives of the impact of MSEs on the improvement of the quality of life of the local population (%)

The development of local capabilities has a significant impact on fostering business development in communities. By strengthening the skills and capabilities of the local population, a more skilled and entrepreneurial workforce is created. This boosts local job creation and promotes the emergence of new businesses in the region, improving the competitiveness of existing businesses, leading to stronger and more sustainable business development. Strengthening local capacities helps the well-being of the population, improving their quality of life and fostering community rootedness, leading to economic growth and social progress in the communities.

Figure 2: Perspectives on the contribution of Local Capacity Building to fostering entrepreneurial development (%)

Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) face a set of opportunities that can make a difference in their development and growth. These prospects, which can open new avenues for their success, encompass several key aspects. With access to credit and loans, these companies can invest in their operations, expand and carry out new projects that will boost their economic growth. In conclusion, these opportunities offer a range of possibilities for the development of micro and small enterprises. With access to financing, participation in public procurement, strategic alliances, sustainability, market expansion and innovation, MSEs can enhance their success and contribute to the economic and social development of the community in which they operate.

Figure 3: Perspectives on the accuracy of opportunities for Micro and Small MSEs (%)

The analysis of perspectives on the measurement of sustainable development in MSEs in the Amazon region highlights their concern for Environmental Impact Assessment, their use of Sustainable Development Indices and their commitment to Social Inclusion. These characteristics reflect a holistic and conscious vision of sustainability, where MSEs seek not only to be economically profitable, but also to contribute to social welfare and respect for the environment, creating a positive and lasting impact on the community in which they operate.

Figure 4: Perspective in measuring Sustainable Development (%)

4. Discussion

There is a need to establish multidisciplinary knowledge management and innovation teams that are responsible for responding to the regional challenges of researching and evaluating promising projects, identifying opportunities at scale, disseminating improved results regionally to increase impact, and to provide a basis for conflict prevention in the commercial, extractive sectors that can create a transitional space in the Amazon. To this end, international organizations or special platforms that can address the challenges facing the Amazon region to "mobilize scientific and technical expertise from academia, civil society, and the private sector with integrated solutions to solve sustainable development problems at local, national, and global levels" (SDSN, 2015). In that sense the implementation of strategies to link micro and small enterprises (MYPES) in Amazonas with the community, academia and public policies through action-oriented research can promote a dialogue and joint search for solutions among the parties involved. This can generate highly beneficial impacts for the region.

The evolution of management and control systems in micro and small enterprises (MSMEs) acquires an environmental and social focus, influencing their impact on sustainable development. These improvements in the management of incoming and outgoing goods, order preparation and inventory control can highlight the relevance of information technologies in MSMEs in Mexico. In a context in Peru where MSMEs are fundamental to increase competitiveness, these technologies offer automation, access to information, reduction of transaction costs and learning processes, contributing to business performance and aligning with sustainability (Saavedra and Tapia, 2013).

In the context of the Amazon region, micro and small enterprises (MSEs) face barriers in the adoption of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), framed in their sustainable development and social environment. An ingrained culture that underestimates the benefits of ICTs and the perception of high long-term investment costs are limiting factors. Addressing these challenges is crucial to fostering an enabling environment where companies can effectively integrate ICTs into their operations, boosting their sustainability and participation in regional development in a meaningful way.

In the local and social context, micro and small enterprises (MSMEs) are of vital importance for sustainable development. In this line, the approach to the incorporation of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in enterprises is no longer limited to debating whether they provide lasting competitive advantages, but to exploring how these enterprises can effectively adopt them to compete, exerting a lasting impact on the social fabric and sustainable economic environment of the region (Ríos et al., 2009). From this

perspective, Jeon, Han and Lee (2006) conducted a study to determine the success factors in the adoption of e-business by small businesses in Korea. In that sense at the local and social level, the study addressed the determinants of success factors in e-business adoption by small businesses in Korea. One of the main drivers was the leader's knowledge of the advantages and benefits of implementing e-business, followed by government support for e-business adoption and the use of e-business as a strategy for globalization and market expansion. Thus, nations that have recognized the strategic role of technology have adjusted their structures to efficiently promote its use, strengthening their capabilities for technological self-sufficiency and innovation, generating an impact on sustainable development and the transformation of their local and social environments.

This perspective seeks to highlight the crucial importance of companies in various aspects, with a strong focus on the environmental, local and social spheres, and their connection to sustainable development. The SMEs studied reveal a limited contribution to sustainable development, indicating the urgent need to implement training and support programs that address corporate social responsibility. These programs can foster effective practices to drive sustainable development (Campos-Campos, Bermúdez-Carrillo, 2020). In this context, the results highlight the imperative of adopting a holistic approach that ensures the teaching and application of deeper knowledge on the subject, thus consolidating the positive impact on environmental, local and social aspects, and moving towards a stronger and more effective sustainable development. The journey towards sustainable development in this region has the active participation of the MSMEs, playing a transcendental role in the construction of a prosperous and equitable future for the Amazon Region.

An important aspect is to take into account the intervention of women, an example of which is the Equal Ecuador Foundation, whose training courses have generated a positive impact that allows the detection of opportunities for the creation of enterprises; therefore, training generates skills and knowledge with respect to the creation of enterprises (Monsalve and Pérez, 2023). Another approach that should not be overlooked is that of women who play a significant role in the rural economy in various functions, such as farmers, paid workers and entrepreneurs. In addition, they play a crucial role in the care and welfare of family members, including the provision of food and care for children and the elderly, and through training, rural women understand how to become entrepreneurs, manage a business and innovate to make it grow. And finally, the importance of public policy to support rural women, the best way is through joint work between universities, society, ministries and key social actors. In this way working for Sustainable Regional Development (Duarte & Guerrero, 2023). In this way, aspects that lead to a good dynamic of opportunities for companies should be taken into account, although the omnichannel has been a breakthrough in the way we interact with customers, unified commerce appears as the next step in this evolution. It is an essential strategy to remain competitive and meet the demands of customers who want to purchase products or services through any channel and at any time. It is the differential that every business needs to offer a truly satisfactory shopping experience (Miranda, 2023).

5. Conclusions

The analysis reveals that the SMEs surveyed in the Amazon region have limited participation in social and corporate responsibility activities, which restricts their contribution to sustainable development. Although the State provides support through various initiatives such as development banking and training, it is crucial to promote practices that encourage both social and corporate responsibility and sustainable development at all levels of business, from SMEs to large companies.

The results highlight that industrial MSEs in the Amazonas region of Peru face long-term survival challenges, with a focus on production under specific orders and local

markets. Participation in export-focused value chains is limited and continuous upgrading is scarce. These findings underscore the urgency of addressing poverty and lack of innovation to boost their development and sustainability.

Sustainable development must be a priority in the business strategy of SMEs, involving all hierarchical levels. This requires training and making each team member aware of his or her responsibilities. In addition, it is essential to implement control mechanisms to ensure the implementation of actions beneficial to the organization.

References

1. Jeon, B., Han, K. and Lee, M. (2006). Determining factors for the adoption of e-business: the case of SMEs in Korea. *Applied Economics*, 38, 1905-1916.
2. Ansoff, H. I. (1965). *Corporate Strategy: An Analytic Approach to Business Policy for Growth and Expansion*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.
3. Diego Campos-Campos Luis Alberto Bermúdez-Carrillo (2020). SMEs, Social Responsibility and Sustainable Development. *InterSedes*, N°43. Vol XXI (2020). ISSN 2215-2458.
4. Duarte Sánchez, D. D., & Guerrero Barreto, R. (2023). Aspects for women's entrepreneurship in rural areas. *Revista Científica Estudios E Investigaciones*, 12(1), 76-89. <https://doi.org/10.26885/rcei.12.1.76>. <https://doi.org/10.26885/rcei.12.1.76>.
5. Fernández García, Ricardo (2011). *The economic dimension of sustainable development*. Spain: Editorial Club Universitario.
6. Galán, José Ignacio & Sáenz de Miera, A. (2012). *Reflections on corporate social responsibility in the 21st century*. Spain: Ediciones Universidad de Salamanca.
7. Gallardo Carlos (2023). This labor market, which is believed to be known, will come to an end. *The economic reality in Peru - General Manager of IPE*.
8. Garrido, Francisco Javier (2005). *Sustainable development and local agenda 21: Practices, methodologies and theory*. Madrid, Spain: CIMAS.
9. INDEPA. (2010). *Ethnolinguistic map of Peru*. <http://www.scielosp.org/pdf/rpmesp/v27n2/a19v27n2.pdf>
10. INEI. (2022). *Informality and the labor force*. Instituto Nacional de Estadística e Informática.
11. INEI. (2014). *Peruvian National Institute of Statistics and Information - National Household Survey 2014b*.
12. IPE - Peruvian Institute of Economics (2023). *The end of the labor market as we know it*.
13. Namakforoosh, Mohammad Naghi (2005). *Research Methodology*. Noriega Editores second edition. Mexico: Limusa 2005 - ISBN: 968-18-5517-8.
14. Miranda Mario (2023). *CEO of Ecomsur by Infracommerce*
15. Monsalve, Yanary Emelina Carvallo; Pérez, Ariana Paola Herrera (2023). *ADRResearch ESIC: International Journal of Communication Research / Revista Internacional de Investigación en Comunicación*. ene-jun2023, Vol. 29, p2-12. 11p.
16. Orbe Chanamé. (2008). *Comentarios a la Constitución*. Fourth edition. Lima: Juristas Editores.
17. UNDP (2016). *Knowledge sharing for sustainable development. The Amazon and the 2030 Agenda*. United Nations Development Programme Regional Bureau for Latin America and the Caribbean.
18. <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/migration/latinamerica/UNDP-RBLAC-AmazonAgenda2030ES.pdf>
19. Ríos, M., Toledo, J., Campos, O. and Alejos, A. (2009). Level of ICT integration in MSMEs: a qualitative analysis. *Panorama Administrativo Journal*, 3(6), 157-179.
20. Saavedra García, M.L. and Tapia Sánchez, B. (2013). *The use of information and communication technologies ICT in Mexican industrial micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs)*.

-
20. Enl@ce Revista Venezolana de Información, Tecnología y Conocimiento, 10 (1), 85-104.
 21. SDSN (2015). SDSN - Vision and Organization. Resource accessed December 20, 2015. <http://unsdsn.org/about-us/vision-andorganization/organization/>.
 22. UNICEF. (2014). UNICEF promotes the first Indigenous Baby Week in Brazil. Brasilia. e
 23. <http://www.unicef.org/peru/spanish/unicef-promotes-first-indigenous-babyweek-in-brazil.pdf>
Wong Cam, David (1997). Big small business. Empresarios y finanzas. Lima: Universidad del Pacífico - Centro de Investigación.